

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

STRUCTURAL ARRANGEMENT OF NOSOCOMIAL MYCOBIOTA AND DISTRIBUTION REGULARITY IN STOMATOLOGICAL CABINETS

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Abstract

The presented work is dedicated to the study of the structural composition and species diversity of the nosocomial mycobiota formed in dental clinics. It was found that the mycobiota formed in dental clinics consisted of 30 species of fungi belonging to 12 genera. It was determined that representatives of 3 genera, including *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus* and *Candidum*, are widespread in dental offices and make up 63.3% of the total mycobiota. At the same time, it was clarified that the density of microscopic fungi spreading in the atmospheric air of dental offices varies between 300-350 CFU/m³.

Keywords: dental clinic, nosocomial mycobiota, structural organization, species diversity, density of fungi, environmental factors.

Fungi living in the environment together with other living organisms have strong competitive ability and are characterized by a fairly wide range of distribution. It should be noted that the violation of the bioecological balance, as in natural ecosystems, has led to these and other changes in the lifestyle of living organisms living in anthropogenic environments, especially microscopic fungi [1; 2; 4]. Thus, in the environment where the navels fall, the hyphal forms related to production processes, large-scale contamination relations with the environment, active metabolism, adaptation to different environmental conditions, rapid transformation into saprotrophic or clinical forms, etc., can be obtained. The fungi that contain the mentioned properties, especially the species belonging to the genera *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Trichoderma*, *Mucor*, *Cladosporium*, *Scopulariopsis*, *Stachybotrys*, *Stemphyllium*, easily migrate to buildings of various purposes, including health care facilities, and after a certain period of time show pathogenic properties and soon pathologies of mycotic origin are manifested [3;6;7]. In particular, the presence of *A.flavus*, *A.fumigatus*, *A.glaucus*, *A.niger*, *A.nidulans* and *A.terreus* species belonging to the genus *Aspergillus* is more dangerous and can be considered a risk factor for the health of patients with low immune status. At the same time, it became known that in any place, including in healthcare facilities, hydrothermal parameters are out of control or the creation of an imbalance situation leads to the enrichment of the pathogenic composition of the formed mycobiota both in terms of number and species diversity, and leads to an increase in the expansion activity of the above-mentioned fungi [9;10].

The purpose of the presented work is devoted to the study of the structural organization of nosocomial mycobiota formed in stomatological clinics and their species diversity.

Material and methods:

The Republican Stomatology Center, the dental clinic of AMU and 5 dental offices operating in Baku were selected as research objects and studied from the mycological aspect. The sedimentation method was used to take samples from the air environment of dental rooms. At this time, Petri dishes filled with Çapek-Doks or Saburo nutrient media were kept open for 30 minutes at a height of 1-1.5 m from the ground. At the same time, samples were taken from the surface of the floor, ceiling, walls, medical instruments of the room, as well as from the oral cavity of the patients by the application method and inoculated in the indicated food environments. Colonies were counted on the 7th day of cultivation. The obtained results were expressed by calculating CFU either in 1m³ air or in 1 g of applied material. In order to obtain a pure culture, it was considered appropriate to conduct the experiments in 4-6 repetitions. Known determinants were used to identify and determine species affiliation of the studied mushroom species.

The frequency of occurrence of fungi is expressed by increasing the ratio of the studied species to the total number of mycobiota by 100 times. Those with more than 40% are considered dominant, those between 20-40% are common, and those below 20% are considered rare [5; 8; 11].

Results and discussion

As a result of our research, it was determined that 30 species of fungi belonging to 12 genera participate in the structural organization of nosocomial mycobiota formed in dental clinics and offices located in Baku (table 1). The comparative characterization of nosocomial mycobiota according to the genus composition clearly shows that 3 genera, including *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus* and *Candida*, are dominant. Thus, *Penicillium* genus 7 species or 23.3%, *Aspergillus* and *Candida* genera each 6 species or 40% make up 63.3% of the total mycobiota. Also, *Alternaria* and *Cladosporium* were represented within the mycobiota with 2 species each or

13.4%. Each of the 7 genera remaining on the ground is 1 species and they make up 23.1% of the total mycobiota. At the same time, the genera that make up the nosocomial mycobiota were analyzed according to the frequency of occurrence and the following results were obtained: *Penicillium* 85-95%, *Aspergillus* 45-50%, *Candida* and *Cladosporium* 40-45%, *Alternaria* 35-40%, *Rhizomucor* and *Rhizopus* 15- 20%, *Eurotium* and *Geotrichum* 10-15%, remaining genera 5-10%. Also, it was found that the average numerical value of the spore concentration collected in the atmospheric air after the sporulation of the microscopic fungi living in the dental offices varies between 15-120 CFU/m³.

Table 1

Structural organization of nosocomial mycobiota formed in dental clinics and offices

№	Genus fungi	Species fungi
1	<i>Aspergillus</i> (1/6)	<i>Aspergillus clavatus</i> Desm; <i>A.fumigatus</i> Fresen; <i>A.niger</i> Tiegh; <i>A.nidulans</i> G.Winter; <i>A.terreus</i> Thom; <i>A.ustus</i> Bainier.
2	<i>Alternaria</i> (1/2)	<i>Alternaria alternata</i> (Fr.) Keissl; <i>A.tenuissima</i> Wiltsch.
3	<i>Candida</i> (1/6)	<i>Candida albicans</i> Berkhout; <i>C.dubliniensis</i> Bucvley; <i>C.glaburata</i> Robin; <i>C.krusei</i> Berkhout; <i>C.stellatoidea</i> Bucvley; <i>C.tropicalis</i> Grenb.
4	<i>Cladosporium</i> (1/2)	<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i> (Fresen) de Vries; <i>C.herbarum</i> Pers.:Fr.) Link .
5	<i>Eurotium</i> (1/1)	<i>Eurotium amstelodami</i> Mangin.
6	<i>Geotrichum</i> (1/1)	<i>Geotrichum candidum</i> Link.
7	<i>Humicola</i> (1/1)	<i>Humicola grisea</i> Traaen.
8	<i>Penicillium</i> (1/7)	<i>Penicillium capsulatum</i> Raper et Fennel; <i>P.citrinum</i> Thom; <i>P.decumbens</i> Thom; <i>P.expansum</i> Link; <i>P.chrysogenum</i> Thom; <i>P.verrucosum</i> Dierckx; <i>P.viridicatum</i> Westling.
9	<i>Scopulariopsis</i> (1/1)	<i>Scopulariopsis brevicaulis</i> (Sacc.) Bainier.
10	<i>Sporotrichum</i> (1/1)	<i>Sporotrichum pruinatum</i> Gelman et Abbot.
11	<i>Rhizomucor</i> (1/1)	<i>Rhizomucor pusillus</i> M.A.Shipper.
12	<i>Rhizopus</i> (1/1)	<i>Rhizopus arrhizus</i> A.Fischer.

It was determined that the density of microscopic fungi spreading in the atmospheric air of dental offices varies between 300-350 CFU/m³. As it can be seen, the mentioned index is quite lower than the micronormal (≤ 500 CFU/m³) determined by the World Health Organization (WHO) for indoor spaces. In our opinion, this is directly related to sanitary-hygienic work carried out in hospital buildings, including dental clinics. Also, despite the satisfactory level of conditions created, the migration of microscopic fungi that are widespread in the environment through the ventilation system to hospital buildings, including the internal environment of dental offices, is an almost unstoppable process. At the same time, the cooling of dental offices through air conditioners leads to a sufficient increase of humidity in the room, which creates fertile conditions for the reproduction of fungi. Therefore, the concentration of fungal spores in the atmospheric air of hospital buildings, including dental offices, is always high, and patients are infected with mycotic pathologies by the aerogenous route.

Thus, the nosocomial mycobiota formed in healthcare facilities, including dental clinics and offices, is characterized by a fairly rich variety of species and mainly acts in the form of bioaerosolized particles.

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